

Workshop: Problems and Prospects of Computational Fanfiction Research

Mia Jacobsen^{1,2}, Julia Neugarten³, Pascale Feldkamp⁴, Yuri Bizzoni^{2,4}, and Ross
Deans Kristensen-McLachlan^{1,2,4}

¹Department for Linguistics, Cognitive Science, and Semiotics, Aarhus University

²TEXT: Center for Contemporary Cultures of Text, Aarhus University

³Department of Arts and Culture Studies, Radboud University

⁴Center for Humanities Computing, Aarhus University

May 20, 2026

*Included in the workshop is a lunch poster session. The poster session is aimed at junior computational fanfiction researchers who wish to present work-in-progress. **If you wish to present a poster, please see instructions in section 5.** Submission deadline: April 24.*

1 Introduction

Fanfiction – stories by and for fans, inspired by existing stories, published online for free – is a burgeoning domain of cultural production. It represents one of the most documented examples of how social communities reinvent, reuse, and develop existing narrative elements and culturally shared memes. Academic attention for fanfiction has grown rapidly in recent years, especially in digital humanities and cultural analytics [2, 1, 5, 3, 8], perhaps because fanfiction offers myriad interesting research questions and lots of born-digital data.

However, working with fanfiction and fan-produced content poses unique challenges for researchers. Data and metadata are often messy, and the ethics of working with fan-produced archives

are complex [7]. In this workshop, we bring together an international group of researchers from different backgrounds, united by their interest in fanfiction. We will facilitate a day of discussion and collaboration, centered around the current problems and prospects of computational fanfiction research, and lay the groundwork for future study.

2 Scientific Scope and Aims

In this full-day, in-person workshop, we will present current research on fanfiction and provide hands-on practical sessions for those looking to work with fanfiction data. There will also be time for group discussion, networking, and a lunchtime poster session for junior colleagues to present work in progress. Our goal is to present the challenges and nuances of working with fan-produced data and to build a network of like-minded scholars.

The workshop has three expected outcomes:

1. **State-of-the-art overview.** Several speakers will expose participants to cutting-edge perspectives on computational fanfiction research.
2. **Hands-on experimentation.** Practical sessions will introduce key fanfiction data sources—most notably *Archive of Our Own*,¹ one of the largest English-language fanfiction websites—and guide attendees through their own experiments.
3. **Community building and collaboration.** By bringing scholars together, the workshop will seed a network within the digital humanities community eager to tackle ongoing research questions in this domain. Working with fanfiction data raises distinctive issues of data management, ethics, and community engagement, offering fertile ground for collaboration.

We have capacity for 25 participants. Table 1 provides an overview of the program. The program brings together a group of international researchers for a mix of activities, including state-of-the-art talks, hands-on experimentation, and time for networking, reflection, and collaborative brainstorming.

¹<https://archiveofourown.org/>

Time	Activity	Speaker
09:30-10:00	Soft start, coffee	–
10:00-10:10	Introduction	–
10:10-10:45	State of the Art of Computational Fanfiction Research	MJ
10:45-11:00	Short Break	–
11:00-12:15	Practical 1: <i>Archive of Our Own</i>	MJ, PF, YB
12:15-13:15	Lunch Break	–
13:15-13:35	Lightnings Talks	–
13:35-14:05	Identifying Sensory Information in Fanfiction	JN, PF, YB
14:05-14:15	Short Break	–
14:15-15:30	Practical 2: GOLEM Knowledge Graph	XY
15:30-15:50	Brainstorm	JN
15:50-16:00	Wrap up	

Table 1: Workshop Schedule

3 Organizers

Mia Jacobsen

PhD Student, Department of Linguistics and Cognitive Science, Aarhus University

Affiliated PhD Student, TEXT: Center for Contemporary Cultures of Text, Aarhus University

Email: mia@cc.au.dk

Mia is currently working on a PhD project that seeks to understand how culture and norms evolve in online fanfiction communities through reader-writer interactions. She has a background in cognitive science and is interested in what cultural artifacts can tell us about the cognitive processes underlying human behavior.

Julia Neugarten

PhD Candidate, Department of Arts and Culture Studies, Radboud University

Email: julia.neugarten@ru.nl

Julia is writing a dissertation about how contemporary online fanfiction on AO3 rewrites Greek mythology. She combines traditional humanities methods like close reading with approaches from computational literary studies.

Pascale Feldkamp

PhD Student, Center for Humanities Computing, Aarhus University

Email: pascale.feldkamp@cas.au.dk

Pascale has a background in comparative literature, studying how literary language evolved as the modern institution of literature developed, with a focus on the high- and low-brow divide. Her research focuses on literary devices, particularly those that evoke sensory and affective experiences.

Yuri Bizzoni

Senior Researcher, Center for Humanities Computing, Aarhus University

Email: yuri.bizzoni@cas.au.dk

Yuri is a computational linguist with a literary background. He has worked on literary analysis and reception, figurative language processing, literary and linguistic evolution, and on developing creative writing software for editorial houses.

Ross Deans Kristensen-McLachlan

Associate Professor, Department of Linguistics and Cognitive Science, Aarhus University

Research Fellow, TEXT: Center for Contemporary Cultures of Text, Aarhus University

Email: rdkm@cc.au.dk

Ross is a cognitive scientist and computational linguist interested in what computers can tell us about how people use language in different contexts. He has a broad interdisciplinary background

applying and adapting computational humanities methods to various textual disciplines, such as Early Modern English drama, sermons of the Danish national church and, more recently, fanfiction.

4 Invited Speakers

Xiaoyan Yang

PhD candidate, ERC-funded project “Graphs and Ontologies for Literary Evolution Models” (GOLEM, 2023-2027), University of Groningen

Email: xiaoyan.yang@rug.nl

Xiaoyan’s PhD explores the role of characterization in literary quality and popularity using a fanfiction corpus. Her research interests include digital humanities, computational literature, cultural evolution, fan studies, knowledge representation, and NLP.

5 Sessions

State of the Art of Computational Fanfiction Research

Fanfiction research goes back to the early 90’s, where it was a primarily qualitative and ethnographic endeavor focusing on the subversiveness of texts. Recently, the myriad of data available online for free has generated increased attention from digital humanities researchers. In this talk, Mia will give an overview of two dominant themes within computational fanfiction research - the style of popular fanfiction and gender (re)presentation in fanfiction - while critically reflecting on how these studies approach fanfiction as an object of study.

Dense Subgroups in Fanfiction Networks

This talk introduces social network analysis as a method for studying communities on digital social reading platforms. Drawing on data from Fanfiktion.de, Germany’s largest fanfiction platform, I examine how subgroups function as interpretive communities within the platform’s usership. Using commenting practices as the basis for a network model that moves beyond individual fandoms, the approach incorporates fanfiction’s three defining components — intertextuality, community, and

quantity — into the data model. The talk follows a three-step network model (comment networks → character relation networks → user-text networks) to uncover community-specific interpretive tendencies. I argue that network analysis’ core strength lies in its data modeling capacity: enabling data-driven grouping and text selection that are invaluable for computational literary studies.

AO3 Practical Session

The hands-on session on working with fan-generated data from AO3 will have a focus on developing research questions and ethically collecting fanfiction data. Participants will be introduced to the AO3 platform, how their data is organized and what kind of data is there, as well as different Python libraries for scraping data.

Lunchtime poster session

The lunchtime poster session provides an opportunity for early-career scholars to present ongoing work in computational fanfiction and gather feedback on their research. If you wish to present a poster, please send an email to the organizers at mia@cc.au.dk. The email must include title, author(s), affiliation(s), and an abstract of max 500 words (excl. references).

The deadline for submitting a poster is April 24th. Poster proposals will be assessed based on the relevance to the workshop. Notifications of acceptance will be sent out on May 4th at the latest.

Identifying Sensory Information in Fanfiction

Fanfiction is characterized by lots of sensory description [6]. In this talk, we present results on extracting sensory information from a corpus of fanfiction about Greek mythology using a lexicon-based approach [4]. This research shows how fanfiction engages with the mythological past and builds imaginary worlds and characters through sensory information.

Working with the GOLEM Knowledge Graph

The GOLEM ontology establishes a framework that defines the interrelationships among key narrative elements and creates a library of modules for these components. Interoperability and integration with existing standards guided its development. Accordingly, the GOLEM ontology provides an extension of the CIDOC-CRM and LRMoo ontologies for cultural heritage, and aligns with the foundational DOLCE-Lite-Plus ontology. This session introduces participants to the GOLEM on-

tology and resulting knowledge graph, exploring their design principles and practical applications. Participants will learn how to apply narrative theory through this semantic model and how to query the graph to explore and analyze narrative data. These techniques are useful when they interact with other knowledge graph-based servers such as Wikidata.

Collective Brainstorm

Julia will facilitate a brainstorm, stimulating participants to develop new directions for computational fanfiction research, including future projects and collaborations, research questions, and digital methods.

6 Prerequisites and practicalities

Participants are expected to bring their own laptop with minimum Python 3.9 installed and an interactive notebook environment such as Jupyter Notebook. Given time constraints, basic familiarity with Python is required (i.e. defining variables and functions, core aspects of control flow, and working with interactive notebooks). Participants will also be expected to perform some pre-workshop setup incl. installation of dependencies. More information will follow.

7 Conclusion

There is a critical mass of researchers interested in computational approaches to fanfiction and other fan-generated data. With this workshop, we believe we can 1) create a thriving network of like-minded researchers centered on this topic, and 2) explore the relevance of using computational methods on fan-produced data, while keeping in mind the distinct methodological and ethical challenges. We look forward to organizing an inspiring, productive, collaborative workshop, and to boosting the visibility of computational fanfiction studies in the digital humanities community.

8 Acknowledgements

This work was partially supported by the Danish National Research Foundation (DNRF193) through TEXT: Center for Contemporary Cultures of Text, Aarhus University.

References

- [1] Judith Brottrager et al. “Character Shifts in Harry Potter Fanfiction”. In: *Zeitschrift für Literaturwissenschaft und Linguistik* 53.3 (2023), pp. 623–654. DOI: 10.1007/s41244-023-00310-5.
- [2] Mia Jacobsen and Ross Deans Kristensen-McLachlan. “Beyond Style: Rethinking Computational Fanfiction Research”. In: *Journal of Data Mining & Digital Humanities* (2025).
- [3] Mia Jacobsen et al. “Patterns of Quality: Comparing Reader Reception Across Fanfiction and Commercially Published Literature”. In: *”CHR 2024: Computational Humanities Research Conference”*. Aarhus, Denmark, 2024, pp. 718–739. URL: <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3834/paper106.pdf>.
- [4] Dermot Lynott et al. “The Lancaster Sensorimotor Norms: multidimensional measures of perceptual and action strength for 40,000 English words”. In: *Behavior research methods* 52 (2020), pp. 1271–1291. DOI: 10.3758/s13428-019-01316-z.
- [5] Julia Neugarten. “A Powerful Hades is an Unpopular Dude: Dynamics of Power and Agency in Hades/Persephone Fanfiction”. In: *Journal of Computational Literary Studies* 4.1 (2025). DOI: 10.48694/jcls.4208.
- [6] Julia Neugarten and Marieke van Erp. “What Fans Think Greek Myth Smells Like: sea, smoke, and flower shampoo”. In: *Digital Humanities Benelux 2025*. Amsterdam, the Netherlands, June 2025. DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.15424191.
- [7] Julia Neugarten et al. “The Powers That Scrape: Ethical Considerations in Using Fan-Generated Data in the Digital Humanities”. In: *Digital Humanities Benelux 2025*. Amsterdam, the Netherlands, June 2025. DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.15600729.

- [8] F. Pianzola, A. Acerbi, and S. Rebora. “Cultural Accumulation and Improvement in Online Fan Fiction”. en. In: *Computational Humanities Research 2020* (Nov. 2020). URL: <http://bura.brunel.ac.uk/handle/2438/21779>.